

Dancing Happiness: Lyrics & Choreography in *Singin' in the Rain* (1952)

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Abstract

Gene Kelly was inspired by the images of happiness in the lyrics of the song 'Singin' in the Rain' when he choreographed the iconic central number of the movie of the same title. This paper investigates how he infused movement qualities, floor patterns and movement motifs with a pattern of increasing joviality that allows dance to incarnate the state of happiness depicted in the song. My methodology is based on Janet Adshead's framework for dance analysis and on Richard Dyer's conceptualization of entertainment as a utopian sensibility that, in American musicals, characteristically portrays utopian feelings, happiness above all.

Introduction

In his collection of essays on entertainment, Richard Dyer claims that Hollywood musicals were 'predominantly conceived of, by producers and audiences alike, as "pure entertainment"' (2002: 19). In Dyer's conceptualization of the term, entertainment is a 'utopian sensibility' (2002: 24) as it was created and perceived by the dominant (bourgeois, white, male) ideology of the capitalist American society (2002: 27). By portraying utopian feelings rather than modelling utopian worlds, American musicals offered images of escapism. Unlike classic utopias such as Thomas More's, they represented what utopia would feel like rather than how it would be organized (2002: 20). And among the range of ideal, joyous feelings they portrayed, Dyer notices that happiness was the main one (2012: 31).

This feeling of joy, just as the rest of the utopian emotions of this form of entertainment, was delineated according to one or several properties that Dyer (adapting Susanne K. Langer's model for music) classifies in five categories: energy, abundance, intensity, transparency and community (2002: 24). Each of them apprehended the emotional signification of entertainment in a different way¹. In the case of intensity, it implied experiencing the emotion 'directly, fully, unambiguously, "authentically", without holding back' (Dyer, 2002: 23).

A prototypical example of this option of presenting entertainment through the portrayal of an intense feeling of happiness is the iconic central number² of the musical *Singin' in the Rain* (1952). Starring Gene Kelly, Donald O'Connor and Debbie Reynolds, and directed by Kelly and Stanley Donen, the film was shot during the golden period of Hollywood musicals. The title number is a solo for a male dancer, conceived as a soliloquy where the main character, played by Kelly himself, shares his happy feelings with the audience. He is on a deserted street, it is dark and it is raining but he is happy (for he is in love) and cannot help feeling wonderful despite the bad weather. The number is built upon this contrast between good inner feelings and adverse external

circumstances. By cheerfully singing and dancing under the pouring rain, the character releases his immense happiness. The intensity is gradually introduced. At first, the character just starts to walk; soon afterwards he proceeds to sing and finally to dance. Both the dance and the music follow the same rising pattern, being increasingly cheerful. This paper investigates the features that delineate this feeling of intense happiness, highlighting the role of music and dance in the design of the utopian option most frequently represented in American musicals³. The music is a song, a musical format that, according to Dyer, is a particularly rich semiotic mix for the statement of feelings in American musicals. It is composed of words, sounds and voice, each with a different role in conveying information (2012: 5). Words name and ground emotions (2012: 5); sounds deploy a wide and nuanced range of affective timbres (2012: 6), and voice mainly adds physical sensation (2012: 7). Here I pay particular attention to words, exploring the way dance takes off from the lyrics, translating their semantic content into dance movements and imagery. To dissect this transformation and examine the choreography, I use the method of dance analysis developed by Janet Adshead (1988). However, since my goal is the exploration of the link between lyrics and choreography, to Adshead's four components -- music, setting, movement and dancer -- I add a fifth element frequently used in the analysis of poems, main motifs⁴.

Music

The first lines of the lyrics of the song read

I'm singin' in the rain
 Just singin' in the rain
 What a glorious feelin'
 I'm happy again
 I'm laughing at clouds
 So dark up above
 The sun's in my heart

Freed in Kelly and Donen, 2001 [DVD]

According to Kelly, the whole number is intended to be a visualization⁵ of these lines (Kelly in Delamater, 1981: 211). They describe both the activity the audience will see, "singing" (and "dancing", as it is also later mentioned in the lyrics), and the circumstances under which it will take place, "in the rain". They also refer to the effect intended with this combination of contrasting elements: to convey a "glorious feeling". The main features of the character and the setting have been thus depicted. Contrasting images have been attached to each of them: an inner sun to the former, and rain, darkness and clouds to the latter.

Setting

The rainy, dark and adverse set is an ordinary street that could be located in any

American town. The dominant colours are brown and grey, but some bursts of bright colours are scattered along the street. The municipal fire alarm posts are red, the diverse plants and trees are green, and white or orange come from the shop windows. These points of colour match with the cheery dancing, reducing the dull atmosphere of the prevailing tones but without completely cancelling its effect. As it is night time, the street is illuminated by artificial streetlamps, with a slightly yellowish quality especially evident when directed towards Kelly's smile. The street is occasionally populated by hasty passers-by who, in accordance with the sober ambience, send reproachful looks to the smiling main character.

Movement

The choreography for the cheerful dancing taking place in this dim setting is organized according to the principle of rising action leading to a joyful climax. Different types of movements correspond to different levels of happiness. The contrast is clear in the opposite dancing qualities of the first and final types of dance: the tap routine and the child-like splashes.

The tap dancing fragment corresponds to the initial release of happiness and takes place in the narrow space of the pavement. Kelly dances in front of the colourful shop windows, facing the road, where the recording camera is placed. The percussive footwork is the most distinctive feature of this dance. Rhythmic sequences enter into a conversation with the melody, offering either an accompaniment or a syncopated counterpoint. The sound made by his feet has an unusual tone, as the generally metallic sound is in this number cushioned and softened by the water (Wollen, 1997: 16). The movement that allows the tap stamping is not heavy, as it takes the smallest necessary amount of weight. His feet make a quick and light contact with the floor, leaving it immediately afterwards. The effect is an impression of lightness. The size of the steps and the space necessary to perform them are small. However, the use of the arms and the umbrella help to create the impression that they are wider. With the same purpose, the dancer generously travels through the horizontal space established by the pavement.

In contrast with these qualities, the jumps and splashes at the end are made of broader and stronger movements, conveying a feeling of extreme happiness. They take place in a big puddle at the left side of the road, where Kelly arrives at the end of the number. At first, he restrains his impulse to jump into it though he starts to amusingly play with the water. Reconsidering his decision, he finally jumps into the puddle. In the steps of this section his legs, not his feet, are the leaders. Always slightly bent, they make very wide movements. The watery ground is either their starting point of contact or their final target. The stress is always put on the moment of touching the ground when the puddle water splashes everywhere. The movement is wide and consciously stressed to humorous effect, with big steps taking up wide space. Kelly moves in all directions. The overall impression is that of a man having the unrestrained and sincere fun of a child. The enjoyment of the performer reaches its climax in this joyful moment. In Dyer's terms, the entertainment value of the film is condensed in these bold steps that shape happiness at the peak of its intensity.

Main Motifs

A similar pattern of progressive development can be found in the choreographic imagery. It relies on the repetition of simple motifs that are subtly introduced on their first appearance but which become more evident and meaningful on their successive appearances. There are three main motifs that I call the “smiling pose”, the “happy rotation” and the “child-like splash”, which respectively stand for the three features of the intense happiness they convey: it can be internally alive despite external adverse circumstances; it can be externalized, producing contagious delight; and it can bring back the child naivety that allows absolute enjoyment.

The “Smiling Pose”

The “smiling pose” is the central motif of the piece and it is the first to appear. Without any musical emphasis, it is briefly introduced at the very beginning of the number, just immediately after Kelly kisses his girl goodnight and turns his body towards the camera. He starts to step down the stairs holding the black umbrella, already open, in one hand but he calmly stops, pausing for a second. The pose is introduced in this moment. He stretches his left hand in order to feel the raindrops falling, while drawing a broad smile in his face, his eyes slightly closed and his head leaning a bit backwards, blissfully facing the cloudy sky. He holds the position for a few seconds, allowing the audience to retain the image of inner happiness despite the external bad weather that is the central motif of the number. Despite its brevity and lack of emphasis, the most important image of the choreography has been established. It will never appear again in exactly the same shape but several imaginative variations occur, each one adding important nuances while conveying the same basic meaning.

The second time the “smiling pose” is used just a few seconds after its introduction a strong musical emphasis accompanies it. It is also preceded by a sudden stop in the movement. This time the gesture is also broader, as not only the left hand but also the right hand stretch out, taking the umbrella with it and leaving the head unsheltered, at the mercy of the rain. Kelly shrugs his shoulders and closes the umbrella, adding an element of carelessness that is the first sign of a hidden childlike nature he will later disclose. The musical stress on the pose is motivated by the fact that here it has an important narrative function: it inaugurates the song.

The most famous variation of the “smiling pose” arrives while the dancer is still singing. With a graceful leap he reaches the top of the streetlamp base, deploying the pose under its yellow light. From that higher level, closer to the unfriendly cloudy sky, his arms wide open and his slightly bent legs gracefully interwoven, he benefits from the brightness of the artificial sun and offers a powerful contrasting image to the darkness in the sky: a sun stands against the rain; his inner joy beams against the adverse circumstances. The pose is sustained for some seconds, marking a pause in the movement but not in the song, which continues to be sung without interruption. The fluidity of the music in opposition to the stillness of the dancer’s body composes the most powerful performance of the pose.

On another occasion, a funny variation of the “smiling pose” is used as an element of

introduction. Placed at the beginning of the dance section, the specific feature of this whimsical variant is that the dancer's knees are bent inwardly, conveying a bold and playful nuance that matches with the tone of the subsequent steps. In addition, the attention of the audience is driven to the legs, not to the generously open arms or the bright smiling face, announcing thus the dominant feature of the dance routine that will follow. Being predominantly tap dance, the leading role will be played by the feet, towards which the eyes of the spectator have subtly been led by the pose.

The "Happy Rotation"

Less pervasive than the "smiling pose", the "happy rotation" motif is placed at the heart of the choreography, between the initial tap steps and the final wild stamps. The motif is again discreetly introduced. Its first shape is a combination of two simple spins on one leg, one to the left and the other to the right. They are inserted in the dance routine but are not particularly stressed. The motif will grow bigger just a few steps afterwards. Opening the umbrella and placing it downwards, the performer dances a whole circle around it, the palm of his hand extended to feel the falling rain suggesting careless enjoyment and spontaneous openness. As if realizing the inherent potential for fun, Kelly abandons the pavement, where he has concentrated his dancing until this moment, and he boldly invades the road. There he dances a huge circle, making precise turns with his open legs while holding the open umbrella outwardly at the waist level. The music heavily stresses this wild whirling as the volume of the melody, at this point already played by the whole orchestra, is opportunely raised. The meaning attached to this motif is that of an unrestrained joy, finally released and overtly announced to the world.

The "Child-like Splash"

The "child-like splash" motif is deeply connected with this idea of uncontrolled and wild happiness that is the dominant feature at the end of the number. However, the motif has been suggested earlier. The way Kelly walks down the street during the opening steps, with the feet coming into a graceful and light contact with the wet pavement before being emphatically raised, is its first subtle manifestation. Secondly, it is implicitly embedded in the tap dancing, where the sound has a particular tone due to the presence of water and where the image of water splashing is already present. In the last and full shape of the motif, the dancer enjoys kicking up water and stomping in the puddle without any restraint. The motif has a significant function, since it marks the end of the rising vitality of the whole number. At this point, the dance reaches the peak of uninhibited enjoyment and culminates the development of the motif that has previously, only slyly been introduced. The effect the "child-like splash" produces in its last appearance is a powerful combination of delight and revisited childhood naivety. It stands for a complete and unrestrained happiness able to produce a deep and lasting impact in the memory of the spectator.

Dancer

The performer of the number, Kelly himself, plays an important role in conveying the feeling of intense happiness embedded in these three motifs. As a dancer, he had an eclectic training that enabled him to offer a broad range of dance expression. His style was rooted in tap and musical comedy dance but also incorporated ballet, modern dance, jazz and gymnastics. In addition, he carefully cultivated his acting skills, as he was always aware that while dancing he was playing a character. His performances were intended to create meaning linked to the story, whether just a vague mood or very specific ideas (Delamater, 1981: 152-156). In this number, his dancing is vigorous, athletic, and vital, conveying an image of lightness, easiness and joviality that matches with the spirit of happiness governing the piece. This image also makes possible that the childlike movements at the end of the dance do not look incongruous but perfectly natural for an adult with an immense inner joy. He wears a grey suit, a light blue shirt, a black tie, a hat and a black wide umbrella. That is, he is dressed as any other man on a rainy evening. The sense of ordinariness conveyed by this costume helps to highlight the universality of the feelings depicted in the choreography. Happiness might be utopian, but gives the impression of being at hand.

Another important contribution of the dancer to the effect of the number is that he skilfully integrates part of the scenery in his performance. As already mentioned, the streetlamp helps him to reach a higher and more illuminated level where his smile seems broader and brighter. He also comically hugs it while he sings he is “ready for love”. In addition, he makes the most of his umbrella. Not only is it the permanent complement for his dancing, in the diverse ways already suggested, but also it stands for a woman, with whom he, amusingly serious, waltzes; and for a guitar, which he plays to seduce the voluptuous woman of the ad at the drug store.

However, objects are not the only target of his attention. He is also aware of the presence of other people on the street. He politely sends the taxi driver away, when he decides that he will rather walk back home; he respectfully greets each of the wet hurried pedestrians he encounters in his way; and he even has a short conversation with the police officer. This final interaction is placed in the closing moments of the number and functions as its appropriately funny denouement. After the sheer delight of watching Kelly’s dancing, the audience is given an opportunity to smile for the last time when hearing the simple and incongruous explanation he gives to the cop’s reproving look at his behaviour on the puddle. “I’m just dancin’ and singin’ in the rain” he sings, and as a result, not only him but also the audience expectant of entertainment is at this point, hopefully, “happy again”.

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Acknowledgements

Grateful thanks to Tamara Tomic-Vajagic and Stacey Prickett, the two intended readers of

this essay at the time of writing. Without their enthusiastic response, it would have never reached a wider audience.

Notes

1. I refer the reader to Dyer for the explanation of how each of these categories have acquired the emotional signification they possess not from their intrinsic properties but from the place they have had within the network of signs in a given culture and at a given point of time (2002: 24).
2. The term ‘number’ is used throughout this paper to refer to the segments of dance and/or music embedded in the narrative of film musicals and distinctive of this kind of movies.
3. The number and the film have been widely analysed from the perspective of film studies. For different examples, see Altman (1987), Fordin (1996), Wollen (1997), Clover (2002), Cohan (2002) and Dyer (2012).
4. I use the term ‘motif’ in the sense of ‘the concrete realisation of a fixed abstract idea’ (Würzbach, 2005: 323).
5. Stephanie Jordan defines the term visualisation as ‘the technique of creating concurrence or imitation between music and dance’. It is possible to visualise many different aspects of music, such as dynamics, textures, pitch contour, instrumental layout, etc. (2000: 74). Here I only concentrate on the visualisation of the lyrics.

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